

ENGAGING WITH OPEN DATA THROUGH VISUALISATION AND COMMUNICATION: THE ROLE AND POSSIBILITIES OF CARTOGRAPHY

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Many uses of open data rely on being mapped – that is, provided with a spatial reference to their particular location on Earth. For example, various socio-economic indicators can be mapped on top of residential districts. Soil quality data can be linked to digital elevation models to model erosion potential, and the same soil data can be compared to geographically overlapping land ownership and land subsidy data. Because human activities are largely confined to the near-surface of the Earth, many open datasets would have far less impact without their spatial component.

By applying different visualisation techniques and tools, various socio-environmental problems can be analysed more deeply, because many sets of data can be observed together, regardless of whether they refer to the physical or social world. For example, to illustrate the effect of a green infrastructure development program, instead of images and tables "locked" in a PDF document, the visualisation of this data on a map can provide a common basis for experts from different domains in researching public policy approaches to mitigate the effects of heat islands in urban environments.

In an era of open data, visualisation tools and technologies are essential to analyse the large amount of available data sets and to make data-driven decisions. Effective visualisation can help in the effort to make mutual relationships obvious, to recognize the impacts of different actions more clearly, and to model and evaluate compromises between possible solutions. As a result of the visualized data being comprehensible to a wide audience, public policy makers can use the visualisations to engage and use the collective intelligence of different stakeholders in the collaborative and democratic development of solutions (Nash et al., 2022).

Although the concept of data visualisation is not new, developments in technologies and analytical tools have changed the way visualisation is done and expanded its application and relevance. With the widespread use of data and statistics for planning and commerce in the 19th century, the practice of transforming quantitative data into visual results has its roots in cartography. Ptolemy's map, known in the 2nd century, marked geographic longitude and latitude with lines, visualizing for the first time phenomena that did not physically exist.

Today, with open data and open technologies, the production of mapping visualisations is becoming more accessible than ever. Although graphic designers and cartographers still play an important role, data-driven communications are not the exclusive domain of these professionals. Instead, they are increasingly used by a variety of knowledge workers (including developers, researchers, journalists, civil society organisations, and businesses) – for their own use or to inform others. As a result, mapping visualisations have been identified as a strategic advantage for the popularity of open data, and they continue to be one of the entry points for the public to engage with open data.

Although the specific goals may vary (e.g., depending on the specific societal question being addressed), the overarching goal of these maps remains the same: to make complex issues understandable to a broad audience and to persuade users of the mapping visualisations to engage and take action.

However, the creation and use of maps for such efforts is not straightforward. Research (e.g., Chess and Johnson, 2007; Ansari et al., 2022; Fish, 2020; Kraak, 1998) has shown that simply presenting facts is often insufficient for someone to take action to address these types of socioecological problems. Not only must the information be presented accurately, but it must also appeal to readers' emotions (Fish, 2021). Design defaults or visualisation limitations in common mapping software packages and application programming interfaces (API) can result in unintended communication consequences (Ricker, 2020).

Therefore, it is important to examine the conditions under which such mapping visualisations are created and disseminated and are thought to foster processes of meaning making, learning, and engagement. Understanding who creates these mapping visualisations and what techniques they use to make them engaging or not is important to assessing the power of visualisation to multiply the impact of open data.

We explore the following questions: Who produces and disseminates mapping visualisations based on open data? Were they created in-house or reproduced from other sources? What themes/topics and geographic extents are represented in the mapping visualisations? What types of cartographic methods (e.g., map type and visual variables) were used, and how successful were the methods used in moving beyond mere description and reporting to engaging and inspiring action. Answering these questions will shed light on current trends in open data visualisation and better illustrate the ways in which modern cartography can better engage and serve citizens through visualisation and communication.

The research methodology included the identification of use cases for the visualisation of open (government) data and the analysis of their characteristics. The basic criterion for selecting use cases was that the visualisation is openly available on the Internet and created with open data (as the main source). The use cases for mapping visualisations were found using search engines under the keywords "Open Data Mapping Visualisation", "Open Data Map", "Open Data Cartographic Visualisation", "Open Government Data Map" and "Open Government Data Visualisation". Based on the requirements, 23 use cases for open data visualisations were found at different organizations. These included public organizations at different levels of government (EU, national, regional, local), businesses, research institutions, and non-profit organizations.

The evaluation of the collected maps is based on content analysis, a systematic approach already used in cartographic research to analyse and compare maps (Muehlenhaus, 2011; Fish, 2017; Roth, 2015). The content analysis method is based on the identification of a set of codes that serve as operational rules that define the definitions and intensity of the different components in the maps analysed. Ideally, the use of codes ensures that each map is systematically evaluated and analysed in exactly the same way so that the results can be compared. It also allows for further analysis by other researchers in the future.

The coding scheme was created to understand the content contained in the maps in terms of: the source of the data, the target group for which it is intended for, who provided the data for use, under what conditions (license) the data are available, and the characteristics of the cartographic visualisation: static or dynamic - interactive or view only, structure type (sequential or non-sequential), and type of navigation: thematic, spatial, and temporal. It was also investigated whether accessibility for the visually impaired or the mechanisms for sharing and embedding content in different environments were implemented.

Preliminary results show that a total of 21 maps contain open government data, while only two maps are based on data collected data. Since maps can have multiple target groups, 17 use cases are for citizen use, 13 are for expert use, and 12 are for government organizations and institutions. As for the data providers, the governmental data are provided by various governmental institutions and organizations, and the datasets collected by volunteers are associated with the citizens' initiative *eBird* and the academic project *Stanovanje plus*. On the other hand, of the 21 use cases, 9 are available under the license type CC (CC-BY and CC-BY-SA), 3 are available under an open government license, while the remaining licenses are either private or unspecified. In terms of map type, only 3 maps are dynamic, of which two are interactive and one is viewable. Of the remaining 20 static maps, 18 are interactive. It should also be noted that only one map from the observed use cases is sequential; it shows data about health in Germany in the form of a narrative map. The maps were also analyzed by navigation type. Since a map can contain multiple navigation types, the total number of navigation types exceeds the number of map examples. In total, there are 18 maps with the possibility of spatial navigation, 11 with thematic navigation and 10 with temporal navigation.

From the results obtained, it appears that most of the maps are static and that most of them are maps where the user can customize the display to his own needs. It can also be seen that about half of the maps have thematic and temporal navigation, indicating that there is an awareness of giving the user the possibility to choose the content to be displayed as well as its temporal comparison. In addition, in most cases the maps are based on open government data, which may indicate that this data has better thematic coverage or is more accessible to the general public. It is also interesting to note that only half of the examples (12) are available under "open" licenses, while for the others the license does not clearly indicate how they can be used. It is also clear from the results of the analysis that cartography plays an important role in conveying information from open data, which can be concluded from several use cases. The use case "Identify your watershed and sewer system area", which allows the user to determine the basin, underwater area, and area of the sewer system for address, shows how a map with only three pieces of data can convey information much more clearly than any other means of communication. In addition, the use case "An Interactive Visualisation of NYC Street Trees" which shows the variety and quantity of street trees in the five boroughs, demonstrates that the representation of spatial relationships does not

necessarily have to include traditional cartographic representations, indicating the possibility of adapting cartography to new trends and needs. This is also supported by the fact that five of the use case maps encourage action through visualisation (visual thinking), as opposed to traditional information transfer (visual communication). This confirms the importance of cartography as a mediator between data and the needs of modern society.

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